

HARMONIC ELIMINATION IN MULTILEVEL INVERTERS USING GRAVITATIONAL SEARCH ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

In the recent years, the modern electrical power generation and distribution systems are moving in a direction where the renewable energy sources are receiving importance. In renewable energy generation, Power electronic converters play a major role. Apart from the conventional three level inverters, to synthesize better power quality AC output, Cascaded H-Bridge Multi-Level Inverters (CHBMLI) are used to obtain more sinusoidal output with reduced harmonics and Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), low dv/dt, lesser switching stress across the devices. The Selective Harmonic Elimination (SHE) is one of the PWM techniques used to remove selected lower order harmonics from the AC output of the inverter. The switching angles of the MLI are obtained by solving the set of nonlinear trigonometric transcendental SHE equations. In this work, the selective harmonic elimination problem is applied to 3 phase seven level and eleven level CHBMLI. The switching angles are considered as optimization parameter with varying modulation index and constant input DC sources. The mitigation of 5th and 7th order harmonics for the seven-level and 5th, 7th, 11th and 13th order harmonics for the eleven level inverter is the optimization targets. The results are compared with the already reported results obtained using Differential Search Algorithm and the Firefly Algorithm. The novel algorithm Gravitational Search Algorithm is used for the estimation of the switching angles and modulation index.

Keywords — *Selective Harmonic Elimination, Harmonics, Multilevel Inverters, Modulation Index, Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)*

1. Introduction

The global scenario towards green energy has led the scientists and engineers to look out for every source of electrical power that is derived at minimal initial and running costs and causing minimal pollution. The renewable energy sources like wind energy, solar PV source, the Fuel cell and some of the energy storage systems like the battery and the superconductive electromagnetic energy storage systems and so on are used in collaboration with either an inverter or a converter [1]. Power electronics based converters are becoming popular in the backdrop of the increased usage of renewable energy sources like wind energy, solar energy etc., The output of the PMSG is usually rectified into DC form and then inverted to the AC form with the required number of phases, frequency and phase [2]. Solar energy is basically in the form of DC. Inverters are used along with them in both grid integrated systems as well as standalone systems. Depending upon the nature of power conversion, the type of power electronic converter is chosen. Then depending upon the power handling capacity required the components and the topological arrangements are made. Further considering the stability of operation of the converter under consideration, proper control schemes are also included. Then, on considering the required power quality of the output of the power converter, the modulation schemes are selected. In the modern trends, the quality of power is improved substantially with the contributions of the topology of the power converter, the PWM technique and the control system. Inverters have gained popularity, these days, because, some of the widely deployed renewable energy systems primarily deliver DC power [1]. The solar Photo Voltaic systems and the Fuel cell systems are examples of sources that deliver DC at the primary level of generation.

Therefore, for a standalone application or a grid-integrated system, it is essential that power efficient and power quality conscious power conversion scheme that is required to convert DC into AC is essential. Inverters of a large variety of topologies are available for this purpose. Even though the source voltage (which may be AC or DC) is in the continuous form, the output of the converter is primarily discontinuous and it requires suitable filters to deliver the output power in a continuous manner and with the required waveform.

Inverters designed with power electronic switches causes pollution in the power systems in the form of harmonics. Harmonics are voltage or current components that are of integer multiples of the frequency of the fundamental sinusoidal voltage or current wave. Harmonics are of the sinusoidal waveform at frequencies of odd integer multiples of the fundamental waves.

An appropriately designed control system basically meant for regulating some of the parameters of interest of the power electronic converter; it also helps to deliver power at the required quality. The development of the modern engineering materials in general and the power electronic semiconductors, in particular, have also contributed greatly for the development of the modern power electronic converters from basic converters [3].

The Multilevel Inverters have received significant attention in the past couple of decades and so many contributions have been done by many researchers for the development of the MLIs. Many directions of research have been looked out with the intention of improving power quality, reduction of mathematical overheads, reduction of cost, improved reliability with proven stability.

The advancements which have taken place in the field of MLIs include topological modifications, improved PWM techniques, advanced control systems and the extension of the MLIs for different fields of applications[4]. Some researchers worked with creative ideas of enhancing the topological structure, and some have worked on the improvement of the performance of the MLIs with advanced control systems. And, some of them have adopted the contemporary technological developments with which they have believed that specific processes which could not have been carried out with earlier technologies. And, it has now become possible with the advent of modern technological developments including the advanced microcontrollers with 16 or 32-bit digital processors, the digital signal processors and the FPGA implementations.

The advent of modern digital computer has led to the development of many advanced simulation tools which have paved the way for developing many advanced software tools that include optimization algorithms[5]. Handling and solving equations with a large number of data or handling a set of data with complicated mathematical interdependence as given by the trigonometric transcendental equations were challenging before the advent of the modern digital computational systems.

2. Multi-Level Inverter

Multilevel inverters are more recent inverter topologies which can deliver output AC voltage waveform with multiple voltage levels in each half cycle. Multi-level inverters the advantages of producing output voltage waveform as close to the sinusoidal waveform. Power electronic inverters are discretely switched inverters with distinct output voltage levels. With more voltage levels in the output of the inverter, strategically placed the THD of the waveform is reduced at the production level itself and hence simple passive filter arrangements would be sufficient to filter out the harmonics[6]. The popular types of Multi-Level Inverters include the Diode Clamped or Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) type, the flying capacitor type and the cascaded H bridge type. However, the cascaded H bridge inverter requires as many isolated DC source as the number of H bridges being used [4].

In cascaded H bridge MLI, the DC sources to be used for each H bridge should be isolated as well as their voltage levels should be either equal or of a finite ratio with each other, typically 1:2:4 or 1:3:9. Also, the MLIs can be realized with a reduced number of switches [7] to reduce switching losses, hence improving the efficiency [8]. When an MLI of cascaded H bridge type is in operation[9], the variations or deviations of the predesigned DC voltage levels will degrade the quality of the output voltage waveform. Like the three level inverters in the case of MLIs also, there are several PWM techniques. The Sinusoidal PWM, the Space Vector PWM and the SHE PWM can all be implemented in the case of MLIs as well. For the implementation of Sinusoidal PWM in the case of MLIs, a multicarrier scheme is usually adopted. In the implementation of SVPWM for MLIs usually, the number of Switching Vectors and the number of elements in each of the switching vector are more as compared to that of a three-level inverter. Also, SHE PWM is one of the low-frequency PWM techniques[10].

Like the single pulse, PWM implemented in a three-level inverter, in the case of the MLI, for each voltage level there will be only one pulse and the width of the levels decrease as the levels increase. Such a modulation scheme is called step modulation. Step modulation or SHE in MLIs guarantee the mitigation of select lower order harmonics by the selection and implementation of the appropriate switching angle or step angle for each step. With step modulation of an N level inverter, with appropriately selected N switching angles, $(N-1)$ lower order harmonics can be eliminated.

3. Solving Methods of SHE Equations

The estimation of switching angles in the context of Selective Harmonic Elimination requires the solution of a set of equations called the SHE equations. The set of SHE equations comprises of n number of trigonometric transcendental equations. If an n level inverter is designed, then n equations are formed relating the n switching angles. The left hand side of the n number of SHE equations, comprising of the n switching instants or switching angles, equate on the right hand side to the amplitude of the fundamental or the amplitude of the harmonics of interest. When these equations are solved, a solution set consisting of the n switching angles are obtained. Using these switching angles, in the step modulation scheme of the MLI, guarantees the removal of the $(n-1)$ lower order harmonics and that the required amplitude of the fundamental is also achieved[11].

The eleven level inverter typically uses Five H Bridges, a seven level inverter requires Three H Bridges and the five level inverter requires Two H Bridges. In all these configurations, the DC supply for the individual H bridges are isolated but of equal magnitude. Such multi-level inverters are known as the symmetrical multilevel inverters. In another configuration, known as the asymmetrical configuration, while using less number of H bridges, it is possible to obtain more number of voltage levels, by maintaining the DC source voltages unequal, but according to some strategy. Of the set of n trigonometric transcendental equations, $n-1$ equations are equated to

mitigate $(n-1)$ harmonics. One among the n equation is meant to make the amplitude of the fundamental at the desired level.

The n numbers of SHE equations use n variables and some trigonometric terms. These equations are not simple algebraic equations. There are two situations where numeric solution procedures could be suggested. In the case of solving a set of simultaneous equations where there are a vast number of variables but the equations are just algebraic, then numerical solution methods could be used. For example, while it is possible to solve a set of two simultaneous equations with two variables using a simple algebraic procedure, it becomes difficult to solve a set of 10 simultaneous equations which use ten variables.

The other situation, where we require numerical solutions, is the finding of roots of equations of a higher order. Thus, seeking the solution set of a large number of simultaneous equations, or solving for the roots of equations of the higher order, may become easy and more practical with numerical methods.

Another group of problems where the numerical methods are useful are when the equations to be solved are transcendental with trigonometric or logarithmic or exponential terms. There are some traditional techniques like the Newton Raphson method [12], or resultants of symmetrical polynomials methods [13] have been instrumental with their own limitations like the long processing time, and hectic mathematical overheads if the variables involved are huge.

With the advent of the digital computer and the fast growth of software tools and advanced platforms, the heuristic search algorithms have fast grown with ability to solve problems with multiple variables and multiple constraints. The Genetic Algorithm [14], [15], the Particle Swarm Optimization [16], the Bee Algorithm [17], the Ant Colony Algorithm, memetic Algorithm [18] and Hybrid APSO Algorithm [19] are some of the popular Heuristic search algorithms. Some of these algorithms require proper initialization of the variables to avoid the convergence in the local minima. The Genetic Algorithm, although it does not require any specific initialization, converges to the Global minima or maxima [20]. However, all these algorithms are considered useful for the estimation of the switching angles for the implementation of Selective Harmonic Elimination PWM. The merit of such algorithms are based on the time taken for convergence, the memory requirements if implemented in the digital processors, the mathematical overheads in terms of the number of calculations and of course the accuracy.

In this work, the evolutionary algorithms like Gravitational Search Algorithm (GSA) is projected. The Gravitational Search Algorithm is a nature-inspired algorithm and the strength of this algorithm is the strength of our understanding of some of the basic laws of physics that have been proved in a deterministic manner, rather than simple observations, mainly, the law of Universal Gravitation. It is used for improving its performance in finding global optima instead of sticking in the local optima. This algorithm is applied to SHE problem of multilevel inverters in finding optimal parameters like switching angles with varying modulation index and fixed input DC sources.

4. Overview of Multilevel Inverters

In work done by the authors in [4], they have done a detailed literature survey related to all the developments that have happened during the last 30 years before 2010. In the research work done by the authors in [21], the authors have compared the performance of the popular multilevel inverters like the Diode Clamped or the Neutral Point Clamped inverter, the Flying capacitor inverter and the Cascaded H Bridge Multilevel Inverter. The implementation of the SHE PWM technique for a seven-level inverter has been demonstrated by the authors in [22]. The authors in work [23] have developed an Artificial Neural Network based switching angle estimation for an eleven level inverter. In the research work carried out in [23], the authors have adopted the Genetic Algorithm for the estimation of the switching angles for the step modulation of a seven-level inverter using a set of three cascaded H bridge modules. The Bee Algorithm (BA) based Optimization technique has been used by the authors in the research work done by [17]. The objective function has been coined with the ultimate aim of mitigating certain lower order harmonics while maintaining the amplitude of the fundamental at the desired amplitude level. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is also believed to be an efficient optimization technique and this technique has been inspired by the social behavior of animals and birds in decision making. The PSO technique is a well-documented and well codified procedure and has been proved to be an advanced search technique in a multi-dimensional search space. The authors in [26] have developed the PSO for estimating the switching instants of a multilevel step modulated inverter. However, considering this particular drawback of the PSO, the authors in [27] have developed a modified PSO, namely the species based PSO or SPSO. The authors, in the presentation of the research in [18], have promoted the SHE PWM as a way of reducing harmonics as well as conversion losses and for improved power conversion efficiency.

Intending to develop an optimization scheme, for the estimation of the switching angles, for the Symmetrical and Asymmetrical configurations of MLIs, the authors in the research work [28] have developed a novel switching instant estimation scheme using the Colonial Competitive Algorithm (CCA). The proposed idea has been derived and modified from the standard CCA to suit the task at hand. The authors have established that the proposed CCA algorithm has outperformed the existing algorithms like the PSO and the GA. The authors have also

verified the results obtained from the proposed idea with a standard seven level cascaded H bridge inverter and have proved the validity of the proposed optimization technique.

The authors in the research contribution [29] have developed a novel switching instant estimation scheme for the multilevel inverter using the Bacteria Foraging Algorithm. In another research work [30] have presented a novel method is estimating the switching instants for a multilevel inverter using the Bacteria Foraging Algorithm. A PSO based switching angle estimation scheme has been proposed and validated for an asymmetrical cascaded H bridge 11 level inverter by the authors in [16].The authors in [31] have developed a novel implementation of the firefly optimization algorithm for the estimation of the switching angles of a multilevel inverter. The Law of Gravity, in the perspective of interaction of masses, based optimization algorithm, has been used by the authors in work [32]. An interesting example of finding the optimal solutions for the optimal power flow using the Gravitational Search Algorithm (GSA) has been demonstrated by the authors in [33]. The authors have used the GSA for the determination of the optimal settings of control variables of the Optimal Power Flow problem.The authors in [34] have presented the methodology and the results of applying a Multi Objective Gravitational Search Algorithm for the generating schedule problem in a multiple process energy generation system.[34]have developed an induction generation based renewable energy source for isolated and standalone applications where there is no grid connection. In the research work conducted by the authors in [35],have adopted a novel technique for the extraction of parameters of a solar PV panel that is essential for the modeling and simulation studies. A population-based search algorithm has been exploited by the authors [36]in which the authors have divided the whole search process into two phases.

Many algorithms have been demonstrated for the parameter extraction of the solar PV panels. In the research work carried out by the authors as presented in [37], the authors have adopted the Gravitational Search Algorithm for the estimation of the system parameters. The novelty of the work consisted of the inclusion of the chaos theory and modified the basic GSA. The Back Tracking Search Algorithm and the Differential Search Algorithm has been used by the authors in [38] for the estimation of the switching angles of the Multilevel inverter. Many researchers have attempted to include the chaos mapping principle in the generation of random numbers that could be needed in the conventional heuristic search algorithms. In this perspective, the researchers in [31] have developed a novel Firefly algorithm (FA) that includes the chaotic mapping for improved global search behavior.

5. Selective Harmonic Elimination for 11 Level Inverter

With step modulated CHBMLI, with n levels, if the steps are strategically timed then, a certain number of lower order harmonics equal to $(n-1)$ will be eliminated. The selection of the timings of the steps can also be constrained in such a manner that the CHBMLI delivers the desired amplitude of the fundamental component. The selection of the step angles or the switching instants of the CHBMLI involves the solution of a set of simultaneous trigonometric transcendental equations[39]. Many solution procedures are available for solving the SHE equations[38]. Let S be the number of levels and V_{dc} be the applied DC voltage for each bridge. The expression of the stepped 11 level AC output as given by Fourier series expansion can be given as Equation (5.1-5.6)

$$V(\omega t) = \sum_{n=1,3,5}^{\infty} \frac{4V_{dc}}{n\pi} (\sum_{i=1}^s k_i * \cos n\theta_i) \sin \omega t$$

.....(5.1)

Where S is the number of levels and n is the harmonic order. The set of equations describing the SHE PWM are given as

$$h_1 = \sum_{i=1}^5 k_i * \cos(\theta_i) = m * s \quad (5.2)$$

$$h_5 = \frac{4V_{dc}}{5\pi} [\sum_{i=1}^5 k_i * \cos(5\theta_i)] = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

$$h_7 = \frac{4V_{dc}}{7\pi} [\sum_{i=1}^5 k_i * \cos(7\theta_i)] = 0 \quad (5.4)$$

$$h_{11} = \frac{4V_{dc}}{11\pi} [\sum_{i=1}^5 k_i * \cos(11\theta_i)] = 0 \quad (5.5)$$

$$h_{13} = \frac{4V_{dc}}{13\pi} [\sum_{i=1}^5 k_i * \cos(13\theta_i)] = 0 \quad (5.6)$$

where θ_i is the i^{th} switching angle, of the five switching angles $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4, \theta_5$. It is assumed that each of the DC sources V_{dc1} through V_{dc5} have deviations from the nominal DC link voltage of V_{dc} . The factor by which the DC sources may differ from the nominal voltage is k_i and $k_i = \frac{V_{dci}}{V_{dc}}$, V_{dci} is the DC voltage supplied to the i^{th} H Bridge. V_{dc} is the nominal value of DC voltage. For an eleven level inverter since there are five bridges and for a seven-level inverter since there are three bridges, i vary from 1 to 5 or 1 to 3 respectively. If the $k_i = 1$ is assumed for all the i values for seven level and eleven level MLI, then the input DC sources are of equal constant values ie., nominal DC link voltage.

Equation (5.2) ensures the desired magnitude of the fundamental component. The remaining equations (5.3 to 5.6) are meant to mitigate the lower order harmonics 5th, 7th, 11th and the 13th. The 9th order harmonic is not considered. Being a three-phase inverter, the 9th order of harmonics is eliminated or mitigated naturally. The modulation index m can be used to control the magnitude of the fundamental component. If N numbers of harmonics are to be eliminated then $(N + 1)$ switching angles should be estimated. The modulation index m relates the amplitude of the fundamental at the output of the inverter and the input DC voltages. The expression relating the DC input voltages and the amplitude of the fundamental component the output of the inverter is shown in Equation (5.7).

$$m = \frac{h_1}{4 * s * V_{dc} / \pi} \quad (5.7)$$

From Equation(5.7), it can be asserted that by changing the modulation index m , the amplitude of the fundamental component can be changed. The range of m over which it can be changed is from 0 to 1. In Equation (5.7), the variable s corresponds to the number of levels. If the V_{dc} voltages applied for all the bridges are equal and V_{dc} then the amplitude of the fundamental component can be simplified as Equation (5.8)-(5.9).

$$h_1 = \frac{m * 4 * s * V_{dc}}{\pi} \quad (5.8)$$

For an eleven level inverter with a modulation index m the fundamental component in terms of V_{dc} and m will be

$$h_1 = \frac{m * 20 * V_{dc}}{\pi} = 6.369 \times m \times V_{dc} \quad (5.9)$$

The maximum value of the amplitude of the fundamental attainable is with $m = 1$ is $6.369 V_{dc}$.

6. Problem Formulation

The SHE equations are very comprehensive and that they can be used in any optimization tool so that the modulation index or the input DC voltages or the switching angles could be estimated for the given values of the other two variables.

The objective function to be minimized for the implementation of SHE PWM is given in Equation (6.1):

$$f = \min_{\alpha_i} \left\{ \left(100 \frac{V_1^* - V_1}{V_1} \right)^4 + \sum_{h_s=2}^s \frac{1}{h_s} \left(50 * \frac{V_{h_s}}{V_1} \right)^2 \right\} \quad \dots (6.1)$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, s$

For a step-modulated multilevel inverter, the necessary constraints to be satisfied is given in the inequalities (6.2),and (6.3). The constraint as regarding the Switching Angles are

$$0 \leq \theta_1 \leq \theta_2 \leq \theta_3 \leq \theta_4 \leq \theta_5 \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (6.2)$$

Regarding the Modulation Index, the constraint is

$$0 \leq m \leq 1 \quad (6.3)$$

As per the fitness function or the objective function shown as Equation (6.1), V_1^* is the desired value of the fundamental component, h_s stands for the order of the harmonics to be minimized and s denotes the number of switching angles. In the fitness function, as shown in Equation (6.1), the error between the desired and the actual values of the fundamental component is controlled and the error is forced to be below 1%. The presence of the specific lower order harmonics is forced to be less than 2%. These constraints comply with the IEEE standard IEEE519 [40].

7. Gravitational Search Algorithm

The Gravitational Search Algorithm (GSA), which had been developed by [32], is based on the principles of Newtonian laws of Gravitational force of attraction between bodies in free space. In the GSA each member involved in the search process, generally known as the agents, are treated as objects having specific masses. Each of the agents is associated with a position, an inertial mass and a gravitational mass. The objects are subjected to the gravitational interaction and the lighter objects are attracted and moved towards the heavier mass. In this evolution, the position and the gravitational mass of the objects or agents are modified.

The force of attraction between two masses depends directly upon the individual masses and indirectly upon the square of the distance between them [36]. The Universal Law of Gravitation is given by the Equation (7.1),

$$F = G \times \frac{M_1 \times M_2}{D^2} \quad (7.1)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the masses of the bodies and D is the distance between them and G is a constant known as the gravitational constant. When several masses are interacting in an isolated system, then the forces on each other leads to the model of a multi-dimensional problem. When the masses of the participating members, the distance between each of the participating members and the forces measured between them are represented by numerical values, the system may undergo a dynamical condition and eventually reach a state of equilibrium. If the system is initially in an equilibrium state and if the mass of any of the members or particles or the masses of some of the members or particles are changed, then the interconnecting forces and the inter-particle distances alter to attain a new equilibrium state eventually. This phenomenon is used in the Gravitational Search Algorithm. The position vector

becomes the solution vector and the fitness of each agent is calculated by the inertial and the gravitational masses of the agents. Thus the position of the i^{th} agent in a N agent system is given as Equation (7.2)

$$X_i = (x_i^1, \dots, x_i^d, \dots, x_i^n) \quad (7.2)$$

Where I stands for the agent number and d stands for the dimension number.

According to the Newtonian law of gravitation, the force of attraction between the agents or masses which are randomly initialized can be given as Equation (7.3). The variables j and i are used to denote different masses and $F_{ij}^d(t)$ means the gravitational force on i by j is given by the Equation (4.3)

$$F_{ij}^d(t) = G(t) \frac{M_{gpi}(t) \times M_{gaj}(t)}{R_{ij}(t) + \varepsilon} (x_j^d(t) - x_i^d(t)) \quad (7.3)$$

$$R_{ij}(t) = \|x_i(t), x_j(t)\|_2 \quad (7.4)$$

In this Equation, M_{gpi} is related to mass of the ' i 'th agent, M_{gpj} is related to mass of ' j 'th agent, while $G(t)$ is gravitational constant at time ' t ', ε is constant of small value and Euclidean distance of two agents ' i ' and ' j ' is $R_{ij}(t)$ is given by Equation (7.4).

The arbitrarily weighted sum of the d^{th} component due to other agents is the net force on agent ' i ' in d^{th} dimension equation is

$$F_i^d(t) = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N \text{rand}_j F_{ij}^d(t) \quad (7.5)$$

At time ' t ', the acceleration of the agent ' i ' of mass ' M_{ii} ' is given by the law of motion,

$$a_i^d(t) = \frac{F_i^d(t)}{M_{ii}(t)} \quad (7.6)$$

The velocity of an agent is updated based on a calculation, which is the sum of its acceleration and a fraction of its current velocity. The present velocity is modified by the acceleration of an agent and a portion of its present velocity to give the new velocity and hence the new position equation is expressed as

$$v_i^d(t+1) = \text{rand}_i \times v_i^d(t) + a_i^d(t) \quad (7.7)$$

$$x_i^d(t+1) = x_i^d(t) + v_i^d(t+1) \quad (7.8)$$

During the search operation, G is also changed as time evolves. The accuracy of the search process is governed by the value of $G(t)$, which is the gravitational constant. In this context, the G is a time variable function and is given as $G(t)$ with the initial value denoted as $G(0)$.

$$G(t) = G(G_o, t) \quad (7.9)$$

$$G(t) = G_o e^{-\alpha \frac{t}{T}} \quad (7.10)$$

The fitness of each agent is found by the values of the inertial and gravitational masses. The most efficient of the agents is the one which is heavy and is being experienced by more gravitational forces and walks slowly, The inertial and the gravitational masses of the objects are modified as per Equations (7.11)-(7.13).

$$M_{gai} = M_{gpi} = M_{ii} = M_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (7.11)$$

$$M_i(t) = \frac{\text{fit}_i(t) - \text{worst}(t)}{\text{best}(t) - \text{worst}(t)} \quad (7.12)$$

$$M_i(t) = \frac{m_i(t)}{\sum_{j=1}^N m_j(t)} \quad (7.13)$$

$\text{fit}_i(t)$ is fitness value of i^{th} agent at time ' t '. For minimization problem, the worst and the best optimum values find out from (7.14)-(7.17).

$$\text{best}(t) = \min_{j \in (1, \dots, N)} \text{fit}_j(t) \quad (7.14)$$

$$\text{worst}(t) = \max_{j \in (1, \dots, N)} \text{fit}_j(t) \quad (7.15)$$

Similarly for maximization problem,

$$\text{best}(t) = \max_{j \in (1, \dots, N)} \text{fit}_j(t) \quad (7.16)$$

$$\text{worst}(t) = \min_{j \in (1, \dots, N)} \text{fit}_j(t) \quad (7.17)$$

In the GSA as the search process evolves in time, every agent is found to occupy a location in the search space. It gives the solution vector of the agents. The locations of each agent are modified in each iteration and eventually, all the agents reach a final unique position, which is the final required result.

7.1 GSA based Selective Harmonic Elimination of MLI with Equal DC Sources

Initially, by considering the switching angles only as optimizing variable, 5th and 7th order harmonics are selected to eliminate for the seven-level inverter. Also, the fundamental component is preserved in the output. The algorithm finds the optimal switching instants for fixed DC voltage and the given range of modulation index between 0.1 to 1. The results are shown in Table 7.1. Here, the magnitude of the selected harmonics is very low in the range of 0.02% to a maximum of 2.14 % for the 5th order. And, the magnitude is in the range of 0.08% to the maximum of 2.3039% for the 7th order. The algorithm efficiently mitigates the harmonics even in the lower modulation indices. The waveforms of output phase voltage, line voltage and their corresponding harmonic spectrums are shown in Figure 7.1(a) to 7.1(d) for the modulation index of 0.5. For this case, the magnitude of 5th order harmonic is 0.52 % and 7th order magnitude as 0.08%. The

THD value of phase voltage is 23.07% due to the increased magnitude of 3rd harmonic and it will be minimized in three-phase. Hence, the THD of the output line voltage is reduced to 13.8%.

Figure 7.1 (a) Output Phase Voltage Waveform

Figure 7.1 (b) Harmonic spectrum of phase voltage

Table 7.1 Seven level inverter input variables and output parameters with equal input sources

θ_1 (Degrees)	θ_2 (Degrees)	θ_3 (Degrees)	M	THD (%)	V1 (V)	V5 (%)	V7 (%)
25.86	59.89	88.81	0.1	29.38	36.21	0.19	2.30
26.50	59.20	89.81	0.2	28.32	35.90	1.12	1.58
20.45	56.14	89.68	0.3	22.81	38.18	0.71	0.20
26.21	59.50	89.57	0.4	28.52	35.95	0.80	1.81
20.47	56.06	89.61	0.5	23.07	38.24	0.52	0.08
12.79	42.59	85.35	0.6	18.69	45.63	0.02	0.20
18.75	44.78	63.56	0.7	22.75	53.52	0.22	0.42
7.02	31.64	60.42	0.8	13.49	59.52	2.14	1.30
8.10	31.13	60.21	0.9	13.16	59.65	1.80	0.86
10.11	30.17	60.48	1	13.06	59.62	1.51	0.28

Figure 7.1 (c) Output Line Voltage Waveform

Figure 7.1 (d) Harmonic spectrum of Line voltage

Figure 7.1 Simulation results of seven-level inverter using GSA with equal input sources

Similarly, for the eleven level inverter, 5th, 7th, 11th and 13th harmonics are chosen for elimination by optimizing five numbers of switching angles. The results are reported in Table 7.2. Here, the magnitude of 5th harmonics is suppressed to the minimum of 0.22% to the maximum of 3.48%, 7th order between 0.3% to 2.04%, 11th order between 0.03% to 0.59%, and 13th order between 0.03% to 1.627%. The THD is also varying from 18.9% maximum to 11.19% minimum. The waveforms for the modulation index of 0.7 are shown in Figure 7.2 (a) to 7.2(d).

Figure 7.2 (a) Output Phase Voltage Waveform

Figure 7.2 (b) Harmonic spectrum of phase voltage

Figure 7.2 (c) Output Line Voltage Waveform

Figure 7.2 (d) Harmonic spectrum of Line voltage

Figure 7.2 Simulation results of eleven level inverter using GSA with equal input sources

Table 7.2 Eleven level inverter input variables and output parameters with equal input sources

θ_1 (Degrees)	θ_2 (Degrees)	θ_3 (Degrees)	θ_4 (Degrees)	θ_5 (Degrees)	M	THD (%)	V1 (V)	V5 (%)	V7 (%)	V11 (%)	V13 (%)
11.39	34.38	53.97	71.69	89.99	0.10	18.70	68.96	2.82	0.54	0.33	1.36
12.83	34.47	53.62	71.99	90.00	0.20	18.93	68.80	2.09	1.17	0.40	1.63
13.57	32.98	53.29	71.99	89.92	0.30	18.38	69.24	1.81	2.05	0.60	1.06
12.86	33.64	53.31	72.00	89.98	0.40	18.42	69.12	2.02	1.47	0.43	1.31
12.58	34.16	53.24	71.84	89.99	0.50	18.58	69.11	2.05	1.10	0.34	1.57
11.08	29.95	47.35	63.40	88.19	0.60	15.59	76.51	0.22	0.41	0.06	0.07
8.63	27.71	40.78	54.10	73.28	0.70	14.82	89.12	0.71	0.62	0.03	0.07
7.08	21.88	36.98	54.13	72.15	0.80	11.39	91.97	2.53	1.13	0.27	0.25
5.89	21.31	37.21	54.22	72.18	0.90	11.34	92.02	3.11	0.55	0.51	0.04
6.42	20.06	37.35	54.12	72.13	1.00	11.19	92.21	3.49	0.30	0.18	0.90

8. Conclusion

From the results and graph, it can be concluded that Gravitational Search Algorithm is used for the estimation of the switching angles and modulation index is giving consistent results. The obtained optimal switching angles successfully suppress the selected harmonics in the output voltage of 3 phase 7 level and 11 level MLI. GSA is giving better results for this work. The work can be further enhanced for calculating optimal switching angles, modulation index and also the magnitude of the DC sources can also be optimised for better power quality. .

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